

Open Edition Series

**Named entities in digital editions:
Between structured databases
and context-specific annotation.**

Workshop Report

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Friday, 6 March

I. Welcome and introduction

<https://zenodo.org/records/19335369>

Yann Stricker, Ursula Bähler and Muriel Jorge

Yann Stricker introduced the ZDE ([Zentrum Digitale Editionen & Editionsanalytik](#)) as a part of the Universitätsbibliothek Zürich and the Zentralbibliothek Zürich. The Open Editions workshop series, led by the ZDE, aims to emphasise the promise of digital editions to make cultural heritage accessible and usable, especially as there have been many new developments in recent years.

Cooperation between researchers, libraries and technical infrastructures is vital to achieve this goal. The [Open Editions workshop series](#) uses UZH's own projects as starting points for discussions around openly accessible Editions and the resources required.

This workshop's focus is on mark-up and the linking of names, data, metadata within a digital edition.

Ursula Bähler then introduced the project PARES, its team and its project-website (<https://pares.hypotheses.org>). Her habilitation treatise about Gaston Paris was recently re-issued, 21 years after it was first published. Previous projects about and around Gaston Paris include:

1. PHILINGK: A collaboration with Bernhard Hurch at the University of Graz, about Gaston Paris' correspondence with Hugo Schuchardt. (Working with the *Hugo Schuchardt Archiv*: <https://gams.uni-graz.at/context:hsa>)
2. Proto4DigEd: collaboration with Yann Stricker, Elias Zimmermann, Reto Baumgartner, Marcus Zerbst, Rita Gautschy. The Idea was to create a prototype for digital editions using pre-existing tools, creating a handbook that is openly accessible: <https://zde-uzh.github.io/proto4diged-handbook/> (DE) and <https://zde-uzh.github.io/proto4diged-handbook/en/> (EN).

The current project PARES is in exchange with previous collaborators. Sharing knowledge and moving forward together are important.

Muriel Jorge underlined collaboration as one of the cornerstones and mentioned the many participating institutions for example for funds and other resources (like documents, archival materials etc.).

Members of different teams present in this workshop are linked across different projects, further showing the importance of exchange and collaboration.

PARES' main areas of research are precisely the archives and networks around Gaston Paris, so, in a fitting parallel, questions of collaboration and exchange of knowledge are inherently a part of the project's content.

PARES : Goals and tasks

Archives		Networks	
Digitizing	Correction and enrichment of catalogs and research tools	Genesis of knowledge taught by G. Paris	Pedagogical
	Digitization of documents	Knowledge circulation on national and international levels	
Giving access	Online publication of documents		Literary network around G. Paris
	Development of a web portal		
Linking	Development of a database	Esthetics of modern literature and its relationship to medieval philology	Women
	Visual representations of data		
Editing	HTR and tagging	First courses given by G. Paris, often to female students	
	Preparation of critical editions		
Historicizing	Collections' history (correspondence and scientific papers)	Letters between G. Paris and his female correspondents	
	Actors and steps of G. Paris' heritage "aborted" conservation		

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II. Roundtable “Entities and Networks”

<https://zenodo.org/records/19051371>

Chair: Claudia Tassone and Fanny Maillet

Claudia Tassone introduced the session by briefly presenting the speakers and outlining the plan for the first roundtable of this digital workshop. This session will focus on four additional project:

1. Eleonora Norcini (UZH), Luise Pappé (University of Bern)
Arcipelago Ceresa: edizione digitale degli inediti, dispersi, postumi. Gender, plurilinguismo, transnazionalità
2. Stephen Turton (University of Cambridge)
Murray Scriptorium
3. Christian Forney (University of Bern)
République des lettres (fmr. HallerNet)
4. Elias Zimmermann (UZH): Annemarie Schwarzenbach
Digitale Edition der Kleinen Formen und Briefe

As the projects come from different contexts, the language used may vary, and each project is currently at a different stage of development. The session will be organized in two parts: first, each project will be shortly introduced. Thereafter, I will ask some specific questions that each speaker will answer regarding their own projects, in order to have a dynamic discussion. In the end, we will have time for an open discussion, led by Fanny Maillet, in which we warmly invite the public to participate.

Introductions of the projects

Eleonora Norcini (University of Zurich) and Luise Pappé (University of Bern) introduced *Arcipelago Ceresa: edizione digitale degli inediti, dispersi, postumi. Gender, plurilinguismo, transnazionalità*. The project focuses on the digital edition of unpublished and dispersed works by the Italian-Swiss author Alice Ceresa (1923-2001). Particular attention is given to questions of gender and literary genre, as well as to transnationality and multilingualism. The project is funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and is conducted jointly by the University of Bern and the University of Zurich. It is developed in collaboration with the Swiss Literary Archives and the Data Science Lab at the University of Bern. The corpus includes unpublished works, posthumous texts, as well as edited journal articles and essays. The digital edition will also incorporate audio documents broadcast by the *Radio svizzera di lingua italiana* (RSI) in the 1970s.

Stephen Turton (University of Cambridge) presented the *Murray Scriptorium*, a project dedicated to the digital edition of the correspondence of James Augustus Henry Murray (1837–1915), the first chief editor of the *Oxford English Dictionary*, published between 1884 and 1928. The project aims to document the scholarly network surrounding the making of the OED through Murray’s correspondence. A pilot edition, launched in 2022, currently contains 114 letters, including 38 written by Murray himself. The main collection of approximately 7,200 letters is preserved in the Bodleian Libraries in Oxford. These letters reflect an extensive international network: although many originate from the United Kingdom, others were sent from countries such as France and Germany. While the public version of the edition has not been updated since 2024 (<https://www.murrayscriptorium.org/>), the team continues to collect and prepare further material for future publication.

Christian Forney (University of Bern) presented the platform *République des Lettres* (RdL), formerly known as *HallerNet*. RdL is not a single digital edition project but a platform that brings together several research and edition projects. Its main focus is on networks of knowledge in Europe between about 1500 and 1850, especially in fields such as medicine, botany, natural history, and economic thought. The projects hosted on the platform are based at the universities of Bern, Basel, Neuchâtel, and Augsburg. They share the same technical infrastructure, including a common XML/TEI model, shared registers, and links between the different projects. Much of the data comes from earlier research on the Bernese scholar Albrecht von Haller (1708–1777) and his large correspondence network, which began in the 1990s. Between 2018 and 2023, about 5,000 letters to and from Haller and 9,000 reviews written by him were edited. The platform currently hosts three ongoing projects: *Bibliothèques et musées* (Neuchâtel, since 2022), *SwissBritNet* (Basel, since 2023), and *Oikoscientia* (Augsburg, since 2025). The platform is available online at: <https://republique-des-lettres.ch>.

Elias Zimmermann (University of Zurich) presented the project *Digitale Edition der Kleinen Formen und Briefe*, dedicated to the Swiss writer Annemarie Schwarzenbach (1908–1942). The project aims to create a digital edition of Schwarzenbach's short texts and letters. The corpus includes around 510 short texts, such as travel reports, essays, and journalistic pieces, as well as about 650 letters. Many of these materials were previously unpublished or scattered across different publications and archives. Schwarzenbach travelled widely, notably in Iran, Africa, and the Middle East, and her texts often reflect these experiences. The project is carried out by a small team of editors and researchers. Further information about the project and the team is available on the website: <https://annemarie-schwarzenbach.ch/>.

Question 1: Named Entities

Context:

The PARES project aims to make the best possible use of the information contained in the archives relating to Gaston Paris (particularly in his correspondence and notebooks). To achieve this goal, the project team will implement a largely automated process to annotate the named entities taken from the automatically transcribed content, which will be corrected manually by the team according to criteria established for critical editing.

→ The first question of the roundtable was: “While the identification of entities such as people, works, places and dates is a regular feature of this type of approach, what other entities, more specific to your needs, have you taken into account and what difficulties have you encountered in defining, specifying and annotating them in your respective project and have you encountered any issues with your identification of entities?”

The *Arcipelago Ceresa* project is using the usual named entities, such as people, institutions, places, works, events, and quotations. They, however, have decided to additionally work with semantic annotations that are specifically connected to their research area. They thus also include entities concerning transnationality and multilingualism, such as “language/s”, “migration”, “nationality”, and “translation”, and entities concerning gender and literary genre, such as “literary characters”, “cross-dressing”, “gender awareness”, “performativity”, and “queerness”. This decision has however led to difficulties, as especially concerning the topics of gender and queerness, certain passages could be linked to an entity of identity, but also sexuality. Moreover, they sometimes struggle defining which passages should be connected to entities and justifying these decisions scientifically. Additionally, as the texts often do not address these issues explicitly but between the lines, the decision to tag a passage with a certain semantic annotation can be hard to decide. Other issues they encounter are the multilingualism of the project, thus the choice between Italian and German when working with the entities and the variety of text genres they are working with, such as literary texts, newspaper articles and essays.

The *Murray Scriptorum* includes headwords as an entity. As most of the letters they are analysing are discussing words in relation to their meaning, etymology, pronunciation, spelling, or illustrative quotations, the team has to identify the headwords manually, as a context-based interpretation is needed for all these instances. Moreover, the index is limited to solely English words at the moment but will potentially be expanded to cognates of other languages as well.

The *République des Lettres* Team references most entities directly. Some entities are, however, also referenced in the header metadata. They work with the regular entities, but have also added certain entities specific to their research such as the entity “Plants and Fungi”. Moreover, their additional entities are further subdivided. Thus, “Plants and Fungi” is, for example, subdivided into the entities “specimens” and “species”. A specific issue that arises in their project concerning the definition of plants and fungi is that Haller used his own polynomial system to classify plants and fungi that does not correspond to Linné’s binary nomenclature, thus complicating the definition of the plants and fungi. The project also decided that in the context of RdL, the data type “archive” has a different functional role than the data type “institution”: The former is used exclusively to identify locations of historical sources, while the latter is used to reference contemporary institutions in historical texts.

The *Annemarie Schwarzenbach* project works with the standard entities, but has added the entities “Correspondence” and “Travels”, which are specifically connected to Annemarie Schwarzenbach’s literary works. They are thus able to cross reference whole correspondences from one letter to another correspondence. The project has decided to work with different tools, such as Google Sheets, Zotero, and Oxygen (where the xml sheets are done manually). An issue that they have encountered is that there are differences between work entities from Zotero and GND entities. Another issue is that some words are used to describe a specific entity and sometimes are used in a more vague sense. For example, the word “Bible” can only be connected to its vague GND definition. A general question that they had to answer is which terms are important to connect to an entity and which are not.

Question 2: Authority Databases

Context: In order to precisely identify annotated named entities, we will map them using external authority databases. To identify people, places, or other project-specific resources, several databases can be used, e.g. IdRef, GND, BnF for people, Geonames, IdRef, Open Gazetteer for places, etc.

→ The second question was: “Have you linked all or part of the named entities you have annotated to external databases? If so, how did you proceed? Did you pick only one database for each entity category (e.g. only GND for persons), or could the same entity be referenced in several databases? Also, how did you handle cases where the chosen database did not have any information on the entities you wanted to identify?”

As the *Archipelago Ceres* project is still at an early stage they do not yet have a fully formed system of annotation. They are modeling their data within a framework currently and plan to link to several authority databases (wikidata, GND, GeoNames), including specifically an Italian authority database (OPAC SBN). At the moment their data is not yet linked to any external databases. Additionally, regarding the texts, it is not always clear which edition should serve as an external link. Eventually the plan would be to create a TEI entity file. As for the semantic annotation, the idea is to link to external dictionaries, for example specifically to the Oxford Dictionary of Gender Studies.

Murray Scriptorium is linking place names to wikidata and coordinates from Google Maps, person names to VIAF or the Oxford Dictionary of National Biography for British people, and headwords to OED.com. When it comes to headwords, there are exceptions: for example “brean”, which is not in the OED as it is a printing error. It is discussed in a letter however, and so it is included in *Murray Scriptorium*’s own index.

République des Lettres considers linking to external databases as their central task.

A suitable database does not exist in every case, which is particularly true for very specific entity types (say, prize competitions). But in general an object might hold multiple identifiers from different databases.

The following list shows which entities on RdL are linked to which external databases:

- Persons → GND · VIAF · IdRef
- Publications → GND · VIAF · VD16 · VD17 · VD18 · USTC · ESTC
- Institutions → GND · VIAF
- Reviews → GJZ18
- Archives → ISIL
- Places (municipalities only) → GeoNames
- Plants (species only) → GBIF · InfoFlora
- Lichens (species only) → GBIF · SwissLichens · Index Fungorum

For persons the goal is to have at least one identifier, also setting a VIAF number, and to find as many others as possible. *Vertical* linking refers to identifiers being stored in one’s own system. *Horizontal* linking refers to linking between person entities from different projects. This is made possible by Metagrid and identifiers are stored externally. The identifiers are linked within the identity file.

The *Annemarie Schwarzenbach* edition takes 4 out of 5 entities from external data. Persons, organisations (rarely) and places: GND-ID can be changed or added through access granted by ZB Zürich. However, more specifically, for example, not every hotel Schwarzenbach has stayed at has to be recorded in GND, only the

most famous ones are. Places can also be recorded through a geonames-URL. As for her works, the project has a bibliography of their own, in the form of a Zotero entry list, so there is no GND-ID for works. Terms (Sachbegriffe) are taken from GND, but have proven unsatisfactory. Ethnic group names for example, are generally not gender inclusive. They are considering changing those GND-IDs, in order to try to change how GND speaks of ethnicity and gender.

Question 3: Data Enhancement and Networking

Context: The PARES project intends to reveal networks of people, institutions and philological concepts that still elude us today. It will also examine the dynamics at work in the genesis and circulation of philological knowledge and practices. To do this, we will consider enhancing data identified in the archival documents with information extracted from authority databases for people, places, or any other entity type.

→ The third question of this roundtable was: “In addition to the identifiers of the external databases, did you try to retrieve other data in order to enrich your project data? If so, did you implement a system to track the origin of the information displayed and used on your public website? More specifically, did you differentiate between information extracted from a particular repository and information generated by the project?”

The project *Arcipelago Ceresa* addressed data enhancement and networking mostly at a theoretical level. Currently, the edition retains only basic local information, such as names, places of birth, and places of death. The team has considered the possibility of enriching the data by including information from external sources. Any enrichment would be implemented in a transparent way, clearly showing the origin of the external data. This approach is simple to implement but still needs to be fully developed by the project team. A possible source of inspiration for implementing data enrichment and tracking is the *Weber Gesamtausgabe* project (www.weber-gesamtausgabe.de).

Murray Scriptorium does not currently include external information from authority databases. The pilot edition focuses on basic biographical facts, such as life dates, places of birth and death, and occupation. This information was collected from probate records and newspaper or magazine obituaries in periodical databases. Many of the people in the correspondence are not widely known. An exception is the use of the *Personalia* of OED contributors (Peter Gilliver, 2021 version), which is explicitly cited on the website, for example in the note “Reader for OED...” (see the picture).

Name	Sex	Role	Born	Died	Nationality	Occupation	Authorities	Note
Edwin Abbott Abbott	male	correspondent (no letters online)	20 December 1838 Marylebone, Middlesex, England	12 October 1926	English	Headmaster of City of London School (1865–1889) / Author	VIAF / ODNB	
William Johnston Anderson	male	correspondent (no letters online)	10 June 1830 Arbroath, Angus, Scotland	1900	Scottish	Insurance agent		
Sir William Reynell Anson, 3rd Baronet	male	correspondent (no letters online)	14 November 1843 Walberton, Sussex, England	4 June 1914	English	Politician / Lawyer / Warden of All Souls College, Oxford (1881–1914)	VIAF / ODNB	
George Latimer Apperson	male	correspondent (no letters online)	1857	17 January 1937	British	Author / School inspector	VIAF	Reader for OED (credited with 11,000 quotations in 1888); sub-edited in B and C; later drew heavily on OED in compiling his historical dictionary <i>English Proverbs and Proverbial Phrases</i> (1929); also produced <i>A Jane Austen</i> <i>Dictionary</i> (1932); (Gilliver 2000-).

République des Lettres enriches its metadata with information from external sources. For example, a curated set of taxonomic and ecological attributes for plant species is imported from InfoFlora (the Swiss national data and information center for flora), and additional species-level data comes from GBIF (Global Biodiversity

Information Facility). The platform clearly tracks the origin of this information: dedicated fields separate project-generated values from externally sourced ones, and externally sourced data is explicitly labeled on the website so users can see its origin. For instance, the plant species object *Ranunculus glacialis* L. contains external data highlighted on the website:

<https://republique-des-lettres.ch/data/plant/01690>.

Annemarie Schwarzenbach does not currently include extensive enhancement of external entities. While some authoritative data, such as well-known hotels or places like Washington D.C., is recorded using identifiers from the GND, most enrichment focuses on internal project data. For example, the travel entity *USA 1936–1937* has been enhanced with additional descriptive information in the project's register. This approach depends

Ranunculus glacialis L.
Plant / Fungus
Referenced in Letter Plant / Fungus
Core data Historical Roses + transfer

Type	Species (Flowering plant)
Species name	Ranunculus glacialis
Vernacular name	Gletscher Hahnenfuß (Deutsch) Ranonce des glaciers (Französisch) Ranuncolo glaciale (Italienisch)
Classification	> Ranunculaceae
Identifier (base)	GBIF: 3033481

Data from InfoFlora

Link	https://www.infoflora.ch/de/flora/ranunculus-glacialis
Habitat and spread in Switzerland	Kalkamer Gesteinsschutt, Moränen, Felsspalten / alpin / A oberhalb 2300 m
Neophyte	Indigen
Protection status Switzerland	Kein internationaler, nationaler oder kantonaler Schutz
Threat (Europe)	Nein
Threat (Switzerland)	Nicht gefährdet

on the expertise of the team members: in some cases, a PhD student who personally studied the travel route can provide detailed annotations, but this level of knowledge is not available for every entity.

Question 4: Data Reusability

Context: The PARES project will collect and organise a set of data relating to its own research questions. However, in an open approach, we plan to allow the reuse of this data to offer the scientific community an opportunity to answer other research questions not covered by the project. This can be done by storing data in open repositories or by building services and API to query the project's database to answer users' research questions.

→ The fourth question of the roundtable was: “How did you plan the reuse of your data beyond the project's temporal and scientific limits? To what extent do you see the reuse of information obtained in the course of your work on entities as an opportunity to extend, supplement or correct data provided by research infrastructures such as the GND or IdRef?”

The *Arcipelago Cereia* project follows the FAIR principles and works with the Swiss National Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH). Their data will be published on Zenodo with a DOI that will be accessible for a long time. It is stored on the University of Bern IIF server, and the project's audio files are stored on the edition's web server. The data is published under the open Creative Commons licenses.

The *Murray Scriptorium* did not plan for any reuse of data beyond the Murray Scriptorium. For a large-scale project, they would tag the data, create a catalogue and calendar of letters, and add part of speech tagging, and develop a separate search interface to allow it to be searched as a linguistic corpus. Moreover, the full letter transcriptions are under UK copyrights and a reuse of the letters beyond their published form on MurrayScriptorium.org would thus be complicated.

The master data of the *République des Lettres* project is stored as TEI-XML files in a Git repository. Although this repository is currently private, they plan to publish the full data on GitHub (public, versioned, and forkable) and mirror the published dataset to Zenodo to obtain a persistent DOI and ensure long-term archiving. This ensures that the data remains accessible, citable, and reusable beyond individual project phases – independently of the platform’s availability. In addition, the University Library of Bern (UB) enables the assignment of DOIs for editions on RdL. RdL also implements a selective data exchange with external databases. Curated outputs from the platform are propagated back to authority databases in defined cases, for example, GND for the creation of new person authority records for previously undocumented actors and GBIF for the submission of curated herbarium specimen records. The project’s goal is mutual enrichment, meaning that the platform benefits from external authority data – and in turn contributes to the improvement of those infrastructures through carefully curated research data.

The *Annemarie Schwarzenbach* project works with a handmade Zotero bibliography, as Zotero can be shared with other projects and has a group library feature. Their bibliography can thus be used for further research.

Open discussion

→ How do you decide what goes in the header and what is annotated in the text?

Christian Forney: The project applies minimal tagging in the text. Since *HallerNet* was not focused on literary texts, the tagging is relatively simple. For letters, the sender and addressee are not tagged in the body of the text because they are already included in the header. Archival sources are recorded in the header to document provenance but are not tagged within the letters themselves, as this would not make historical sense. Entities are generally tagged only at their first mention.

→ (To *Arcipelago Ceresa*) This specific Gender Studies dictionary (Oxford), how was this source chosen? Why not other options, like *Open Gender*?

Eleonora Norcini and Luise Pappe: The team chose the *Oxford Dictionary of Gender Studies* as an authority source. They also considered other options, such as an Italian-language dictionary or *Open Gender*. Additionally, the team is still reconsidering which type of semantic annotation will be applied to the project data.

→ (To *Annemarie Schwarzenbach*) When do you have enough data to create a person-entry in the GND?

Elias Zimmermann: To create a person-entry, we need the full name and the date of birth or death. It is also preferable to include the person’s profession, and, if possible, the country (which can be the country where they were born, worked, or lived). Sometimes there is not enough information, which makes identification difficult.

Markus Zerbst added that: a person can be added as soon as they can be identified; more details on this will be discussed tomorrow.

→ (To *Annemarie Schwarzenbach*) Is there any control for GND entries?

Elias Zimmermann: Sometimes duplicates occur, but this is rare. When a duplicate is detected, it is shown in the system and can be deleted. A GND number is created instantly. If there is a small mistake (such as a duplicate), it must be corrected: the new number is deleted, and all references in the project data are updated accordingly. This process happens only occasionally.

→ (To *République des Lettres*) How are entries controlled or verified?

Christian Forney: Entry points often come from sources such as the botanical garden of the University of Neuchâtel. Sheets are checked by the responsible team members, and external verification is provided by experts, for example from the botanical archive in Neuchâtel.

→ (To *République des Lettres*) How do you handle entity recognition?

Christian Forney: So far, entity recognition is applied only for named entities and not for assigning them to databases. Language extraction is done using approaches with large language models (LLMs), but other methods are also possible. Using LLMs is interesting, but the results can be influenced by the team's limited expertise with these tools.

→ How do you handle ontology maintenance (e.g., using Wikidata, where information can be added without strict control, versus more stable sources)?

Stephen Turton: The project uses Wikidata for places, but this raises issues. Historical borders change over time, so the data shown today may not correspond to the historical situation. There is also the problem of what happens if a Wikidata entry is deleted, which can create inconsistencies.

Elias Zimmermann: The project uses GeoNames for places and creates or deletes points as needed. Coordinates are recorded from GeoNames, and a Google Sheet stores the coordinates automatically, even if the GeoNames reference is later lost. This ensures that the place name and coordinates are preserved in the project data.

→ (To *Murray Scriptorium*) Identifying headwords can be difficult (same issue for PARES; e.g., the etymology of the French word *trouver* is very broad). How do you manage headwords?

Stephen Turton: For the Paul Meyer correspondence, the project does not annotate etymons. Words that are not listed in the dictionary are generally ignored. The team considers only the exact word as it appears in the dictionary.

→ Do you provide references at the paragraph or sentence level?

Elias Zimmermann: The project generally references the whole text. An intermediate solution is being tested: referencing commentaries in the text (*Stellenkommentare*). Since the commentary can be semantically unclear, the idea is to assign a keyword to the commentary rather than referencing the entire passage. However, implementing this is difficult, as it requires coding a pointer and linking it to the correct keyword, which is tedious.

Stephen Turton: For example, with swearwords, if they are included in the dictionary, editorial footnotes are used. The dictionary word is linked directly to the footnote.

Eleonora Norcini and Luise Pappé: For short texts, it is easy for the reader to read the entire text, and keywords are easy to detect. For longer literary texts, detecting topics is more difficult, as they may appear more implicitly, requiring a different approach.

→ Do any of the projects deal with fictional places, and how do you manage them?

Eleonora Norcini and Luise Pappé: We work with literary texts, which include places, but rarely named characters or fictional places. This is not much of a problem for our project. Unnamed entities do not need to be tagged.

Elias Zimmermann: We do not have fictional places, but we do have persons. Purely fictional persons are not tagged. For biblical figures, there are theological debates about whether they are considered fictional or not. The project lets the GND decide: if the person already has a GND entry, it is tagged; if not, it is not tagged. There could be a category for fictional persons if needed. For places, the main challenge arises when trying to create maps.

Christian Forney: The project focuses on the 17th century and includes religious contexts, so some “places” such as Hell or Paradise appear, along with theological figures and locations. These may be handled as keywords or topics, separate from real geographic places.

→ Where can GND numbers be found?

GND numbers can be found on Wikipedia (similar to VIAF) or by searching directly in the GND database.

III. Roundtable “Infrastructures”

Chair: Yann Stricker

The discussion focused on examining entities through the lens of infrastructures, highlighting the complexity of the task.

1. Marcus Zerbst (Zentralbibliothek Zürich)
Linking authorities – bonus or onus?
2. Alexandre Tur (Bibliothèque nationale de France)
L'indexation au cours du texte dans les catalogues de manuscrits français en EAD
3. François Gandolfi (Humathèque Campus Condorcet)
Le signalement des documents d'archives : interopérabilité et web sémantique
4. Piero Andrea Martina (IRHT Jonas)
Répertoire des textes et manuscrits français du Moyen Âge: Jonas (et au-delà)

Marcus Zerbst: Linking authorities - bonus or onus?

<https://zenodo.org/records/19111878>

Marcus Zerbst started his presentation with a metaphor of his workplace, his house, and his canton in Switzerland to explain what happens when you work with GND: The house representing the editorial office, the groundworks of the house being the framework and conditions of the GND, and the canton/country representing the political implications and civil protection, which contribute to the country's resilience (top down approach fosters orientation), and communities benefit from each other.

The GND is THE German system for entities, containing over 10 Mio. entities. It has controlled, high-quality vocabulary, is freely available, has fast processes and improved visibility. Moreover, if you use GND, you are ensured to use FAIR data. It is used in archives, museums, digital editions, etc.

GND, however, has a multilingualism issue as the GND only includes German vocabulary (it is thus used by international DACH users). A system that provides similar options and recommendations is IdRef. A mapping between GND and IdRef is feasible through VIAF. Moreover, GND is connected with multilingual Wikidata mapping via the reconciliation project. This reconciliation project improves the matching rate of the GND in Wikidata avoiding constraints and increases the quality of Wikidata and the use of GND via Wikidata.

The NFDI (Die Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur) encourages the use and expansion of GND. The NFDI is funded by the DFG (initiative of 92 million Euro), which demands FAIR data.

Zerbst further called to action, asking his audience to advocate at associations, university bodies, and annual conferences a push for a structure for authority data services in Switzerland, which lays a common ground for culture and research. He further encouraged his audience to claim a new GND agency by contributing to the opening of GND for their own domain and contributing with their editorial work and technical support.

He thus concluded that linking authorities is a bonus and not an onus.

After his talk, Zerbst was criticised for his German-minded perspective by a person in the audience and was then asked if authority databases shouldn't be less rigid in a multilingual country like Switzerland. Zerbst answered that a top-down idea could still be useful and that the infrastructure built in Germany is currently funded the best, as it is also funded by the government. A further comment raised concerns that authority data is always linked to an organisation of knowledge, which thus has a normative impact. This person then called for more independent and less normative databases.

Alexandre Tur : L'indexation au cours du texte dans les catalogues de manuscrits français en EAD

<https://zenodo.org/records/19112046>

Alexandre Tur a présenté l'indexation au cours du texte dans les catalogues de manuscrits français en <ead>. Il a d'abord rappelé le contexte du catalogage des manuscrits en France, marqué par le passage progressif des catalogues imprimés aux catalogues numériques. Historiquement, des catalogues tels que le Catalogue général des manuscrits des bibliothèques publiques de France (1849-1993) rassemblent les descriptions de nombreuses bibliothèques. Aujourd'hui, le paysage français s'organise principalement autour de trois grands réseaux : la Bibliothèque nationale de France (BnF), les bibliothèques de l'enseignement supérieur et les bibliothèques relevant de la lecture publique (notamment sous la tutelle du ministère de la Culture).

Dans ce contexte, le format XML/<ead>, développé à la fin des années 1990 aux États-Unis et utilisé en France depuis le début des années 2000 dans les services d'archives, s'est progressivement imposé pour la description hiérarchique des fonds. Bien qu'il n'ait pas été conçu initialement pour les bibliothèques, il s'est révélé particulièrement adapté aux collections spéciales, qui mêlent souvent manuscrits et archives littéraires. L'utilisation de XML permet notamment d'établir des liens hypertextes entre instruments de recherche, entre institutions différentes, ou encore vers des notices d'autorité et d'autres ressources en ligne. Ces notices jouent un rôle essentiel d'intermédiation entre catalogues, permettant par exemple de relier un manuscrit à des éditions imprimées ou à des notices présentes dans d'autres bases de données. Les notices d'autorité permettent de relier les catalogues entre eux, par exemple en renvoyant vers des équivalents dans d'autres bases de données ou vers des éditions imprimées. Elles aident ainsi à dépasser les frontières parfois arbitraires entre catalogues, notamment dans le contexte français où coexistent plusieurs systèmes comme ceux de la BnF, du CCFr et les instruments de recherche en <ead>.

Cependant, plusieurs défis demeurent. L'indexation des entités dans les instruments de recherche est encore largement réalisée manuellement, notamment lors de la conversion d'anciens catalogues papier vers des formats numériques, ce qui représente un travail long. Les fichiers d'autorité peuvent également être lacunaires, notamment parce qu'ils étaient initialement conçus pour les auteurs publiés, alors que les catalogues de manuscrits mentionnent souvent des personnes qui ne sont pas auteurs ou qui jouent des rôles différents, en faisant des personnalités pas forcément publiques. Par ailleurs, l'écosystème français reste fragmenté entre plusieurs catalogues et systèmes d'autorité.

Enfin, Alexandre Tur a évoqué les évolutions normatives en cours, telles que le Library Reference Model (IFLA-LRM) et le modèle archivistique Records in Contexts (RiC), qui encouragent le développement de liens sémantiques plus structurés entre les données. Cela suscite un intérêt particulier pour les catalogues de manuscrits. Une nouvelle version d'EAD est également annoncée pour 2026. Les institutions travaillent actuellement avec la version 2 et envisagent de passer directement à la version 4, en omettant la version 3, même si cette transition ne sera pas immédiate et demandera du temps.

→ Question from the public: For the EAD format, what are the difficulties in moving from version 2 to version 4? Is it not possible to do it automatically?

Alexandre Tur: Some older people hope that the conversion could be done automatically. However, older catalogues contain relatively little indexing. Newer standards encourage more semantic indexing, for example by linking names to authority records. Implementing this would require going back to the existing data and this is not impossible, since it would represent a large amount of work.

→ Question du public : J'étais intéressé par cette possible évolution vers une approche plus encyclopédique. Est-ce quelque chose qui a été envisagé ?

Alexandre Tur : Cette possibilité a été discutée, mais la principale difficulté concerne le contrôle des valeurs d'entrée. Cela impliquerait aussi une évolution de la philosophie actuelle : des fichiers d'autorité initialement conçus pour un usage interne à la BnF devraient être rendus accessibles à un public plus large. On pourrait imaginer un outil unique, co-géré par plusieurs institutions. Une étape suivante pourrait être d'ouvrir ce système à d'autres institutions de recherche. Concernant la question des infrastructures, des essais ont

également été menés avec Wikibase, mais les résultats n'ont pas été jugés entièrement satisfaisants. Par ailleurs, la BnF est actuellement en train de restructurer ses catalogues.

François Gandolfi: Le signalement des documents d'archives : interopérabilité et web sémantique

<https://zenodo.org/records/19112446>

François Gandolfi présente son travail sur les outils numériques de l'Humathèque. C'est là que se trouve la plus grande partie des archives Gaston Paris, à savoir 3 mètres linéaires de documents.

Il constate que les métadonnées documentaires diffèrent entre différents systèmes d'information: souvent la description d'archives se trouve sous forme d'une liste. Il s'agit maintenant de travailler sur le passage d'une liste sur papier à une liste en format XML-EAD.

Exemple: document à gauche et description XML à droite. On observe la hiérarchisation des données.

Manuscript inventory of Gaston Paris's library, 1891-1896. Humathèque, Gaston and Paulin Paris Collection, EPHE BMF 4PAR 133

Extract from the computerized catalogue of the archives of the Condorcet Humathèque, Gaston and Paulin Paris Collection

La structure hiérarchique permet l'héritage des informations des composants hauts vers les composants bas. Donc, l'information prend du sens en fonction de la place qu'elle prend dans le code. Exemple: Un document prend place dans une liste, en tant que composant.

L'organisation physique et matérielle du fonds ne correspond plus à la logique de la numérisation. Il y a un changement de paradigme. On ne décrit plus des documents physiques mais des reproductions numériques. On ne peut donc pas utiliser le même langage. Il est nécessaire de passer à un vocabulaire générique qui peut décrire toute sorte d'objets.

Les deux langages sont développés et entretenus par des organisations publiques. L'interopérabilité entre les deux se construit, on pourra arriver à dériver les infos d'un système à l'autre. Ce changement de langage et d'organisation d'informations nous ramène à une liste de documents, comme sur une liste de papier. L'intérêt est différent. On obtient des métadonnées organisées par 1 champ = 1 valeur. Une valeur en Dublin Core est associée à une clé. Les champs de Dublin Core sont en vérité un peu plus que des clés, mais des propriétés,

elles portent en elles-mêmes la valeur, donc le sens de ce qu'elles décrivent. (S'y ajoutent des liens URI vers des bases d'autorité, par exemple IdRef.)

IdRef est idéal pour cet usage, car cela contient un vocabulaire contrôlé et enrichi par des experts de leur

Encoded Archival Description	Dublin Core
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• A hierarchical descriptive language for archival collections, used to represent the physical organization of archival fonds (in a tree structure).• Highly structured standard serialized in XML format, complex and rigorous.• Formalized by a Document Type Definition (DTD), comprising 146 elements.• International standard maintained by the Library of Congress.• National recommendation in France: EAD en bibliothèque »• Used in archival information systems (SIA) such as CALAMES, TAPIR, and UGEO.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Generic vocabulary intended for metadata and the description of all types of digital resources• A weakly structured, non-serialized standard (CSV, JSON, XML, etc.)• Consists of 15 core elements, with additional supplementary properties• International standard maintained by the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI)• Provided recommendations by the Bibliothèque nationale de France (BnF) or ABES• Used in digital content management systems (CMS) and digital libraries: GALLICA, OMEKA, and for the OAI-PMH exchange protocol

discipline. Les données se rapprochent maintenant de triplets : on trouve une URL correspondant à un document ou un prédicat : l'auteur ainsi qu'un URL IdRef pour l'auteur.

On se rapproche d'un modèle de connaissance qui rappelle le RDF, permettant une autre approche.

Gandolfi montre finalement une *knowledge map*/ un web sémantique construit de documents et de métadonnées.

Pour résumer, la question centrale est la suivante: comment passer d'un modèle hiérarchique à un modèle sémantique?

→ Question du public: Comment identifier une nouvelle personne en France?

François Gandolfi: Dans chaque établissement se trouve un agent qui peut créer une notice d'autorité. Il faut lui donner une notice de document attestant l'existence de la personne. Il faut par ailleurs que ce document fasse partie d'un certain réseau.

Alexandre Tur: Il faut la preuve d'une source.

Piero Andrea Martina (IRHT Jonas) : Répertoire textes et manuscrits français du Moyen Âge: Jonas (et au-delà)

<https://zenodo.org/records/19112610>

Piero Andrea Martina commence sa présentation en expliquant que l'IRHT (L'institut de recherche et d'histoire des textes) est une unité propre du CNRS, qui fournit un répertoire pour étudier des manuscrits et des chartes. Le but de l'institut est d'acquérir des connaissances des textes et manuscrits dans une perspective historiciste; de créer un inventaire des manuscrits du monde, d'en faire une reproduction, de les conserver et d'étudier ces textes. La description d'un manuscrit est faite de première main, donc par contact direct avec le manuscrit. Le projet Jonas a hérité les textes et informations du *Manuel bibliographique de la littérature française du Moyen Âge*. Comme le projet *Jonas* contient énormément de textes, il se concentre sur les textes qui existent déjà dans d'autres bases de données. *Jonas* travaille donc ensemble avec *Arlima* et avec *Arca* (pour voir la reproduction des textes).

→ Question du public: Si un texte est sur *Arlima*, qui contient toutes les informations sur ce texte, et qu'il existe un lien avec *Jonas*, comment peut-on empêcher des duplications?

Piero Andrea Martina: Le risque d'une duplication existe toujours. Avant on ne pouvait pas faire un lien entre une base de données externe si il n'y avait pas de réciprocité avec la propre base de données. Donc *Jonas* n'aurait pas pu faire un lien avec *Arlima* en théorie, mais en pratique le projet a quand même pu lier ces données avec *Arlima*.

→ Question du public: Qu'est-ce qu'on fait avec les titres dans les titres et les textes qui changent de titre? Faut-il prendre les titres du DLF?

Piero Andrea Martina: Oui, on prend les titres du DLF. Dans la bibliographie médiévale de *Jonas*, les différents titres sont rassemblés et liés avec le même identifiant.

Alexandre Tur: Dans les fichiers d'autorités de la BnF, on peut trouver plusieurs titres sous une œuvre, mais pour le moment ces données ne sont pas liées avec *Jonas*.

→ Question du public: Pour le langage des descriptions, documentaires ou archivistiques, est-ce que le langage est structuré et standardisé pour les description d'un manuscrit?

Piero Andrea Martina: Comme le langage est très structuré, cela cause le problème que le code est trop large.

→ Question du public: Est-ce que vous planifiez de modifier ce code ou de développer d'autres infrastructures?

Piero Andrea Martina: Oui, mais ce renouvellement de la base des données et la sécurité de ces données fait peur, car elle pose la question de la pérennité de tout cela.

Saturday, 7 March

IV. Edition model and entities PARES

V. Roundtable “Tools”

Chair: Vincent Paillusson

1. Reto Baumgartner (Science IT, UZH)
Input presentation PARES
2. Antoine Bugnicourt (Huma-Num)
Corpusense et les collections d'annuaires numérisés à la Bibliothèque nationale de France
3. Anouschka Mamie (University of Bern)
Annemarie Schwarzenbach: Formulas, Formatting, and Scripts: Google Sheets as a Lightweight Infrastructure for Digital Editions

Reto Baumgartner (Science IT, UZH): Input presentation PARES

<https://zenodo.org/records/19112803>

Reto Baumgartner presented the PARES project, focusing on named entity recognition (NER) and strategies for identifying entities in digital editions. He emphasized that while some entity identification can be automated, much work remains manual, especially for smaller projects or for cases where context matters. Manual approaches include using applications to mark entities, identify them from lists, and assign IDs, while semi-automated or automated approaches involve tools such as TEI Publisher, GATE, Flair, spaCy, NLTK, HeidelTime, and gazetteers. Tools like OpenRefine allow identification and correction of entities almost fully manually, which is important for high-quality results, though scalability becomes an issue as data volumes increase.

He also highlighted the importance of vocabularies and authority files for people, places, and organizations, including GND, IdRef, VIAF, Wikidata, and GeoNames, as well as standardized formats for dates (ISO). In another one of his projects, Proto4DigEd, he connected TEI Publisher with GND and provided options to map to IdRef. Bibliographic references can be exported from Zotero into TEI, with missing entries added manually. While this approach works for small projects, it raises questions of scalability for larger datasets.

Reto Baumgartner discussed the XML vs plain text challenge, noting that most NER tools are designed for plain text. Using XML can introduce overlapping markup or whitespace issues, especially when sentences or named entities are interrupted by page or line breaks. Despite automation, manual review and post-processing are still necessary to ensure quality, including double-keying and inter-annotator agreement.

Looking forward, the vision for PARES is to combine automated entity recognition with curated metadata in the project database, re-using archival catalog data while keeping human oversight. Open questions remain about which tools to use, how to manage vocabularies, how to handle scalability, and which adjustments may be necessary during the project.

Antoine Bugnicourt : CorpuSense et les collection d'annuaires numérisés à la Bibliothèque nationale de France

<https://zenodo.org/records/19113137>

To start, Antoine Bugnicourt presented the BnF DataLab:

Founded 5 years ago, the idea was to have an entity at the BnF responsible for digital editions. The aim is to help researchers in building their corpus, access data, particularly for copyrighted works.

Establish collaborations between researchers manifesting in three ways:

1. A physical location at the BnF;
2. A range of services provided to support research projects, a collaboration between various departments at BnF;
3. A digital infrastructure to work on corpora outside the public domain.

In partnership with HumaNum (CNRS), Antoine Bugnicourt works for HumaNum in the DataLab. A vast network of researchers and contact to cultural heritage institutions are in place.

CorpuSense is a part of the Mezzano project (following the SODUCO research project). It provides open and interoperable tools for assisted annotation of custom corpora. AI shows the structure of the text, preventing difficulties.

CorpuSense works through a IIIF structure, thus allowing to build a collection and select wanted pages through the Manifest.

From the collection a chain of processes takes place: OCR on collections; extraction of structured data with AI tools; export of structured data in different formats.

Practical example: A study on the influence of female film professionals in French cinema throughout the 20th century:

In order to produce gender statistics, starting with professional directories where gender is not explicitly noted, the goal is to extract as many entries of female professionals as possible. The provided data include name, profession and address. The extraction and sorting of data into categories, allows one to deduce information on gender of natural persons.

A manifest can be copy-pasted into a text-field or a file is imported to CorpuSense. To get relevant information from the pages of the directory, it is then tagged on the scan of the page. To this effect, a generic prompt can be used, as the page is clearly structured as a list of entities. Then, specific fields of information listed are defined. (For example: First name = first part of named entity.) At this stage one can also try to extract inferred data, for example gender.

Some limitations of the tool: As there are around 4000 items, some errors can occur, mostly due to layout of text, or through arbitrary errors by OCR. These errors can all be checked and changed manually. Ambiguous interpretations also have to be checked at this stage. There has been a 94% accuracy for gender detection.

As it is an LLM-based approach, there is some bias in providing context for some data. Accuracy of prompting proves to be quite important. Experiments have to be repeated sometimes to get accurate results.

The tool is easy to use once you know how to. A next goal would be to advertise it for diverse uses. Before that however, better quality control strategies have to be thought of.

Ultimately, the idea is to have replaceable modules, to use different APIs and different tools in workflows. It remains a work in progress.

→ Discussion: A short discussion was held about the decisions concerning the number of gender identities to include. Furthermore, names that aren't clearly associated with one gender are an additional difficulty. There were no conclusive answers yet, but they remain important questions to consider.

Anouschka Mamie: “Annemarie Schwarzenbach: Formulas, Formatting, and Scripts: Google Sheets as a Lightweight Infrastructure for Digital Editions”

<https://zenodo.org/records/19113259>

Anouschka Mamie explained how her goal is to improve workflows and not to create new ones. The *Annemarie Schwarzenbach* project uses Google Sheets as a central hub, as it serves as a lightweight infrastructure for digital editions. She explained how these sheets are created manually. She showed an example of how the entity of “people” is connected to project specific ID’s and is linked to a GND-entry. Moreover there is a section which shows the person’s connection to other people. Here is an example of how they manage the “people” entities:

Example Sheet: Personen

Personen	Label [generiert, nicht manuell bearbeiten]	Publiziert	Tr Nachname	Tr Vorname	Variante, Spitz	GND	GND_Search	Geburtsdatum	Todesdatum	Typ	Tr Bemerkungen
person_0001	Auerbach, Erich	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Auerbach	Erich		https://d-nb.info/gnd/1194	yes	1911	1977		Bemerkungen
person_0002	Beneš, Edvard	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Beneš	Edvard		https://d-nb.info/gnd/1186	yes	1884	1948	Historische Person (d)	Bemerkungen
person_0003	Bieberle, Emil	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Bieberle	Emil			https://web.bsz-bw.de/				Bemerkungen
person_0004	Bodmer, Marie-Louise	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Bodmer	Marie-Louise		https://d-nb.info/gnd/1357	yes	1911	1999	Freundin	Bemerkungen
person_0005	Bodmer, Robert	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Bodmer	Robert			https://web.bsz-bw.de/	1894	1947		Bemerkungen
person_0006	Bourdet, Claude	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Bourdet	Claude		https://d-nb.info/gnd/1192	yes	1909	1996	Freundin	Bemerkungen
person_0007	Boveri, Margret	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Boveri	Margret		https://d-nb.info/gnd/1188	yes	1900	1975	Bekannt	Bemerkungen
person_0008	Breslauer, Marianne	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Breslauer	Marianne		https://d-nb.info/gnd/1189	yes	1909	2001	Freundin	Bemerkungen
person_0009	Briol, Paul	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Briol	Paul		https://d-nb.info/gnd/1348	yes	1889	1969	Bekannt	Bemerkungen
person_0010	Burckhardt, Carl Jacob	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Burckhardt	Carl Jacob		https://d-nb.info/gnd/1188	yes	1891	1974	Freundin	Bemerkungen
person_0011	Cadisch, Martha	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cadisch	Martha		https://d-nb.info/gnd/1359	yes	1910	1994		Bemerkungen
person_0012	Burckhardt, Elisabeth	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Burckhardt	Elisabeth		http://d-nb.info/gnd/10781		1913	1954	Bekannt	Bemerkungen
person_0013	Carter, Paul	<input type="checkbox"/>	Carter	Paul			https://web.bsz-bw.de/				Bemerkungen
person_0014	Chim	<input type="checkbox"/>	Chim			https://d-nb.info/gnd/1195	yes	1911	1956		Bemerkungen
person_0015	Clarac, Claude	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Clarac	Claude	Achille	https://d-nb.info/gnd/1081	yes	1903	1999	Freundin, Familienar	Bemerkungen
person_0016	Clerc, Charly	<input type="checkbox"/>	Clerc	Charly		https://d-nb.info/gnd/1048	yes	1882	1958		Bemerkungen
person_0017	Cram, Lisa von	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cram	Lisa von	Dobeneck, I	https://d-nb.info/gnd/1249	yes	1912	1975	Freundin	Bemerkungen
person_0019	Faure	<input type="checkbox"/>	Faure	Jacques			https://web.bsz-bw.de/				Bemerkungen

The pros of working with Google Sheets are that it is easy to use, low cost, the set up is quick, it allows for real-time collaboration, and it has a flexible structure. Moreover, one can improve the workflow by including integration and automation processes.

The cons of working with Google Sheets is that it is not built for entity management, it is not a database and it, for example, does not support complex relational structures between people. Moreover, there is a data integrity risk as it is done manually, which can lead to duplicates, typing errors etc. Another issue is the scalability, as the more the data set grows, the more the loading time slows down. The loading time is moreover dependent on the infrastructure of Google. Another con is that it has a weak access control with no fine-grained options.

However, there are certain options that can fix or optimize these limitations. Working with formulas, for example, automates calculations and data logic, which fastens the workflow. Moreover, formatting improves the structure, the clarity, and the visual control. Working with scripts can automate and customize the workflows and advances the processes, thus allowing for a powerful automatisisation. These scripts, however, require a familiarity with Java script.

To demonstrate these optimizations, the formula to optimize the unity of the spreadsheet was presented. It is important to know that there are tutorials on Google Sheet functions.

Using FORMULAS, formatting, and scripts

- Example: **label generation**
- The Label is a cleaned-up concatenation of the Nachname, Vorname fields. This process is done automatically with a formula.

Code, field B2

```
=GLÄTTEN(SÄUBERN(WENN(ODER(A2="";C2=FALSE);"";WENN(UND(D2="";E2="");"";WENN(D2="";E2;D2 & WENN(E2="";""; " & E2))))))
```

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Tr Person-ID	Label [generiert, nicht manuell bearbeiten]	Publ. ziert	Tr Nachname	Tr Vorname
2	person_0001	Auerbach, Erich	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Auerbach	Erich

Another example was made about the reduction of duplicates through conditional formatting, which was run over GND ID's to find potential duplicates (which can be used over several columns).

Using formulas, FORMATTING, and scripts

- Example: **spotting duplicates**
- Each entity should be recorded only once. The GND ID serves as a unique identifier and is therefore a reliable indicator of duplication. A custom conditional formatting rule checks column G, where the GND links are stored, for duplicate entries. If a duplicate is detected, the corresponding cell is highlighted in a designated color.

Code, column G

```
=ZÄHLENWENN(G:G;G1)>1
```


Some links / tutorials:

Guide by howtogeek: [How to Highlight Duplicates in Google Sheets](#) (02/03/2026)

Moreover, custom scripts were presented, which allow to detect information about a person and automatically add them to the spreadsheet.

Using formulas, formatting, and SCRIPTS

- Example: **get info from GND**
- Some of the collected information is already available via GND. Once the GND link is entered (column G) and confirmed (column H), selected data fields—in this example: birth year—are automatically retrieved from GND and populated in Google Sheets.

Google Apps Scripts:

JavaScript

Some links / tutorials:

Google Apps Script overview: [English](#) / [Deutsch](#) (02/03/2026), Guide by spreadsheetpoint: [Easy Beginner's Guide](#) (02/03/2026)

`=getBirthyearfromID(H377;G377)`

	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
	Label [generiert, nicht manuell bearbeiten]	Publ. ziert	Tr Nachname	Tr Vorname	Variante; Spitz	GND		GND_Search	Geburtsdat	To de sd
	Silone, Ignazio	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Silone	Ignazio		https://d-nb.info/gnd/11871	yes		1900	1978

Using formulas, formatting, and SCRIPTS

- Example: **accelerate manual GND look-up**
- After manually entering the last name and first name, a script generates a code that creates a clickable search link to the GND results. The link opens in the browser for verification. Once the definitive GND link is entered and confirmed, the temporary search link is automatically removed to maintain clarity and keep the sheet organized.

Sidenote:

Feel free to reach out if you'd like to learn more or use the code snippets. While they are relatively simple, they are tailored to our specific Google Sheets setup and would need to be adapted to your own structure.

Tr	Nachname	Tr	Vorname	Varia nte; Spitz	GND	GND_Search	Geb urts dat	To de ad
Akaygen		Jalé				https://swb.bsz-bw.de/		
Akaygen		Enis			https://d-nb.info/gnd/14261	yes	1880	1956

Lastly, one can add GND suggestion links in the spreadsheet, which allows for a semi-automatic approach to find links when one enters the name or surname of a person in the spreadsheet, which then leads to a suggestion of a potential GND number, which can be confirmed or denied manually.

The conclusion of the talk was that Google Sheets can be useful for small projects in which entities are manageable, as the semi-automated approach requires an overview of the entities in order to not lose track of the data. The sheets can be easily customized and there are easy ways of coding, which allows people without programming background, to work with Google Sheets.

Open discussion

→ (To *Annemarie Schwarzenbach*) What you presented is ontology management and ontology integration. Why do you need representations for persons that are already on GND? Why not only do it for people that aren't already on GND? Why this choice, are there any specific needs?

Anouschka Mamie: What's helpful is that you can use them to get a drop-down menu in Oxygen. You can have your data available (collected for specific needs).

→ (To *Annemarie Schwarzenbach*) So you need an overview of your data? Even though many of them are already in GND? Is it important to have them all in one place?

Anouschka Mamie: Yes. It saved us a day, because we did not need to get the GND references again. Moreover, it is helpful for the nicknames, because with all the columns prepared including all the information about this person, they can only use the nicknames appearing in their document and yet still have access to all the information needed. Additionally, you can add fields you don't have in the GND.

→ (To *Huma-Num*) Since you use AI models over which you don't have control, do you have the experience of made-up data?

Huma-Num: I wasn't there for the experience, but in my opinion, there was only a small percentage of mistakes. Most mistakes were caused by the initial OCR or were interpretation mistakes of the existing data. They thus did not encounter significant issues. He explained that using this AI model was a practical choice. In the future, there is a possibility of changing the model, especially due to the controversial revelations about the AI model they used. Thus the end goal would be to find something more customizable and to be able to choose from a list of AI models or to own custom models that run through data.

→ (To *Huma-Num*) Since there is an act of interpretation, even if the error rate is low, is there a declaration for the users that this data was generated, that it is derivative data that wasn't originally in the source?

Antoine Bugnicourt: I think that would have to be theoretically. As I said early, it's not reliable by itself, it's important to use it as a collaboration in research. It's important to represent how the data have been extracted first. With some examples it works quite well (e.g. actress names that will be available on Internet, not a problem to associate it with a gender). There are issues with gender neutral names (e.g. in french with Dominique) that are ambiguous gender-wise. It is thus difficult to extract information from only a name. These examples are then marked as undefined gender (=0).

→ (To *Huma-Num*) There are also queer personalities, how do you deal with that identification?

Antoine Bugnicourt: This tool is used as part of the workflow. An initial extraction can be used for certain parts of data that are more defined, but CorpusSense does not allow for connection to authoritative files, which would thus need to be improved. There is thus a need for more context and for more diversity in the options. Gender options could be broadened. However, these types of reflections would need to be considered or made before the input.

→ (To *Huma-Num*) About prompt driven information extraction: Is there a role of visual language model that interprets the image/facsimile? Or is it a process of extracting text and analysing that?

Antoine Bugnicourt: A visual approach could be interesting. The idea is that with this tool you have text extraction through visual information, so not a plain text but an annotated text with spatial information. An intermediate solution is to not have images anymore, but annotated text that can be reviewed before the extraction. Even with limited OCR quality you can manually improve the extracted text and provide better spatialised plain text for data extraction later. Continuous improvements are made, however, OCR is visually difficult. It can also be difficult to read handwritten texts, thus visual models can be strong by combining both modalities.

→ (To *Huma-Num*) What is the cost of this tool? Who is paying for the tool?

Antoine Bugnicourt: So far, the tool is hosted by the research engineers at Epita. The Mistral API can be accessed for free. The OCR tool is not self provided but provided by engineers. So far, there is not a lot of traffic so we are doing it ourselves. We are, however, looking for a more stable solution, for example, a partnership for the hosting of the website and the CNRS could take on some costs. But this is a work in progress. As the website is publicly available, these questions need to be answered, as it could lead to errors of loading the website.

VI. Roundtable “Workflows”

Chair: Simon Clematide

1. Johannes Graën (Science IT, UZH)
Input presentation PARES
2. Stephen Turton (University of Cambridge)
Workflow and its tributaries in a UK context
3. Simon Gabay (Université de Genève)
The FreEM project: from digital facsimiles to named entities

4. Peter Dängeli & Levyn Bürki (DSL, University of Bern)
Entities and experiments. Corpus exploration, proto indexing and enrichment workflows

Johannes Graën: Input presentation PARES

<https://zenodo.org/records/19113387>

Johannes Graën presented the initial considerations and workflow of the PARES project. He emphasized that the project is complex, involving many data types, relationships, and collaborators, which makes it essential to model both the data and the processes. His objectives are to make optimal use of the team’s capacity, ensure that everyone is actively engaged, keep track of each step of the workflow for all documents, and reduce the mental load on collaborators. Johannes Graën highlighted that whatever can be automated should be automated.

For the initial data processing, the team spent about six months naming entities. This initial step produced the primary data and part of the secondary data that will be used throughout the project.

Manifest workflow

Johannes also introduced the manifest workflow, which visualizes the order of tasks: deciding which pages to transcribe, how to work efficiently in Transkribus, and how to annotate topics (linked to the ongoing development of the ontology). Metadata is extracted from the original manifest and should flow continuously through the process.

Regarding Transkribus, the data is split into multiple collections. Layout recognition and transcription are applied automatically to all incoming documents as layouts are frequently easy to recognize. Collections are then moved sequentially as needed: from initial processing, to collections requiring different types of tags, and finally to a collection where finished documents are gathered. Text orientation can vary—vertical, horizontal, and occasionally circular—if needed, the layout can be corrected manually, after which the document is queued again for reprocessing with the HTR model. Each movement in the workflow ensures that the data is processed systematically and consistently.

→ Question: How do you move things between collections: manually or through a program?

Johannes Graën: Both. Moving from collection 1 to 2 is manual, and from 2 to 3 is automated. Anything that has to be manually checked is placed manually as well.

→ Question: What about storage? What happens when 3 is full?

Johannes Graën: We have enough storage. Step 3 is reviewed and will not need transcription anymore. Step 3 is around 6 gigabytes, so once it's done, we don't go back to that phase.

We experimented with shadow images of the backside of pages. These could be removed, which would improve picture quality.

→ Question: When you convert to TEI, if you notice a problem at the end, do you have to regenerate the whole thing?

Johannes Graën: We only mark documents as finished when they are actually finished. Changes can still be made in Oxygen if needed.

→ Question: Using a computational linguistics tool, what happens when pages are moved? How do you generate TEI while taking into account changes in page order?

Johannes Graën: You need to specify the page order in the tool when generating TEI.

→ Question: How do you generate IDs for letters and manage them?

Johannes Graën: Transkribus allows us to order titles and keep the original document order. Using a generator, we can assign IDs and the letter number according to the original manifest.

→ Question: Because this would take decades if done manually.

Johannes Graën: With the manifest, we can derive IDs, then convert and generate IDs for different elements.

→ Question: Regarding the IIF Manifest: how does the manifest include correspondence between pages and their authors, since that isn't stored in the manifest?

Johannes Graën: The manifest only contains pages. We have a separate document indicating which authors correspond to which pages. This information is kept under the "page" section.

Data — initial processing

Muriel Jorge: I'm not sure individual letters have EAD, only each person.

Johannes Graën: We have the ID of the starting page. In the database, you can always change.

Stephen Turton (University of Cambridge): *Workflow and its tributaries in a UK context*

<https://zenodo.org/records/19113448>

For the *Murray Scriptorum* project, automation wouldn't be possible because their archive contains hundreds of writers with different handwritings, which would thus require a lot of training for the automation to work. They have editorial protocols for handling their entities. They use the basic tags and their index metadata allows for a map. They have abandoned the practice to name places that are not linked. All the titles of works and the titles cited in editorial footnotes are tagged and linked to their bibliography. At the moment, they still have duplicates in their footnotes and the information in the letter and the footnotes are duplicated between letters. Their headwords are linked to their index. People, such as Murray, are linked to their index, but some aren't. In the beginning, they only tagged the recipient and sender of the letters as people, which is connected to the index. Other mentioned people in the letters are tagged differently.

The index has however been enlarged. A disadvantage is that they have no complete catalogue of Murray's catalogue, so they will need to go back and find people and tag new people in the letters and in the editorial notes. Moreover, people who have sent correspondence are not included when they didn't write letters themselves, so people are missing from their list. A difference they have in their metadata is that since the copyright information in the UK 1988, unpublished works, such as Murray's letters, are under copyright. In 2012, the EU allowed EU states to publish edited versions of works of digital heritage. This has changed with Brexit, so to publish their work would now cost a lot of money. Thus, publishing them will cause difficulties. There are exceptions, but they will need to seek permission. And for other authors, they will need to trace copyright holders, in order to get in touch with them for the copyrights.

→ Question: How do you do bibliographic references?

Stephen Turton: Badly, we didn't include them in the letter transcriptions themselves, but in the footnotes. This was not a good choice, because it causes us additional work now.

Simon Gabay: *The FreEM project: from digital facsimiles to named entities*

<https://zenodo.org/records/19113537>

Through his philological background, Gabay notices and states that computational studies often lack a philological perspective. When looking at models for transcription, it becomes clear that the model often transcribes the same sign differently. So, the question poses itself: Is Optical Character Recognition enough? No, we need layout analysis.

A strategy is needed, that works for texts from the middle ages up until contemporary texts.

SegmOnto: The 3rd version will be published this year. For prints and manuscripts the same zones can be detected.

CATMuS works on texts from the 9th century to today.

CATMuS : key principles

The FreEM project

S. Gabay

[Introduction](#)

[Before NER](#)

[NER](#)

[After NER](#)

Figure: Geneva, ms. Comites Latentes, 102, fol. 122 ra, image from e-Codices

Level	Transcription
Normalized	Ci connance la vie saint Lambert l'ev[es]que et le mar[tir]
Semi-Normalized	Ci <con>mance la vie saint Lambert l'ev[es]<que> et le mar<tir>
Graphemic	Ci 9mance la vie saint lambert leuesq̄ 7 le mar'
Graphetic	Ci 9m[an]ce l[ui]e l[ui]r l[ui]mbat leuelq̄ 7 le m[ar]

Table: Different level of transcriptions

A graphemic approach is the key to build robust multilingual and diachronic models.

In order for everyone to transcribe things the same way, guidelines need to be created based on robust models created by big corpora.

ATR (Automatic Text Recognition): Linguists need a certain type of information, literary scholars other types. So, we have to find a middle-ground. The diversity of languages in the texts, as well as in the different fields of study are an additional difficulty. ATR works on the graphematic level of transcription.

AN (Automatic Normalisation): A translation takes place, starting from the output to a target that we define. So different targets are defined by different factors.

Strata encoding: Depending on what you want to study, a different strata can be used.

Quaero: Is used for named entities (And is also used by *Impresso* (Simon Clematide), with different entities and annotations.) 4.9 mio tokens have currently been annotated.

NER: An additional difficulty: when a named entity is part of the name of another named entity (for example: la cathédrale de Paris).

After NER: SETAF-project: The objective is to read, to do research, not to create infrastructure for infrastructures sake.

With this in mind, the following example was made: A specific project on fights/violence in the French colonies was shown. Data modelling allows us to observe movement and dynamics of persons (criminals and victims) in relation to space.

Finally, it is important that everything should be open source and thus usable for research.

→ Question: How many tokens did you annotate? You mentioned automatic tagging and graphematic transcription?

Around 5 million tokens. Automatic tagging was created through these 5 million tokens. The tokens represent a sample of French literature over 3 centuries, including different spellings and evolving syntax. In order to have a representation of all entities that existed, you need a huge amount of tokens for several examples so that the computer can understand what to do.

→ Question: Would one model focusing on one century be better for a specific context? Is this approach mostly good for cataloging huge corpora?

One model is used per task, including diachrony and diatopy. This strategy includes base models, questions of modelling and a gigantic base model that can be finetuned for a specific context, rather than creating a new model for every specific situation.

→ Question: Does the control vocabulary harmonize with TEI/XML tags? Could nomenclature used in Transkribus then be exported in XML for custom tags?

That should work. The idea behind SegmOnto is to have a layout analysis. Data can be automatically transferred/transformed to TEI, paragraphs remain intact. It's robust for different document genres.

Peter Dängeli & Levyn Bürki: Entities and experiments. Corpus exploration, proto indexing and enrichment workflows

<https://zenodo.org/records/18944194>

Peter Dängeli presented an outlook on how they plan to proceed with the project *Arcipelago Ceresa*. The workflow starts with image digitisation, handled more like a photographic unit, in collaboration with the Swiss National Library (SNB). Using IIIF, they can define the labels of the documents. In Transkribus, the goal is to produce raw transcriptions of the text manually, without specific tagging or layout. The next step is document export, transferring the content into a format closer to what is needed for the project. The transcription and annotation are then carried out in Oxygen XML Editor, while a web application will be built from the TEI source. Name entity deduction and identification will be integrated at the stages of “Document export” and “Transcription & annotation”.

The slide is titled "Edition workflow: Named entities". It contains the following text:

Goal: facilitate manual tagging by creating an automatically compiled list with possible entries (including authority references)

Approach:

- use an LLM to evaluate the raw Transkribus output of each transcribed document and
- detect entities,
- try to link them to one or more authority records, and
- deduplicate the resulting list
- in order to offer the entries in the linking utility in oxygen

We call this a "proto index", an imperfect index of entities that likely occur in the corpus.

It is meant to be a shortcut for the editors that saves them manual querying of authority databases.

The actual entity tagging is done by the editors.

State of work: experimental, explorative (but not too far from production-ready)

At the bottom of the slide, there is a red footer bar with the text: "Arcipelago Ceresa", "Named Entities in Digital Editions, Roundtable 'Workflows', 07.03.2026", and "4 / 12".

For proto-indexing, it is essential to refer to authority records and try to link entries to recognized sources. The term “proto-index” is used because the index is still imperfect.

Their workflow starts with a small tool or interface (MCP) that allows users to interact with the data, followed by a step to enrich it with information extracted from Wikidata.

The slide is divided into two columns, Step 1 and Step 2.

Step 1

Feed documents to LLM and ask to **detect entities**, then **identify** them using Wikidata knowledge.

Using a slim local helper service that acts like a plug-in the model can call (via the Model Context Protocol, a simple way for tools to talk to each other).

This allows to search (e.g.) Wikidata directly (quickly, in memory) without extra servers or manual wiring.

Step 2

Take output of step 1 and **enrich it with Wikidata information**, then generate a **spreadsheet (csv)**.

Simple Python pipeline executing SPARQL queries (no LLM used).

Transparency is important: the prompts used for entity detection are displayed for review. The team then showed some of the prompts they will be using. Currently, the prompts are restricted, but the system could be extended to other pools. Often, queries return empty results, indicating that nothing matching the prompt has been found.

→ Question: Can you repeat which LLM you are using?

Peter Dängeli: Here it is the LLM3, at the moment it is one of the strongest. They also have a cluster that can be used at the university and it is made out of open models.

When gathering data, if the system is asked for a place or person, it will attempt to search for a corresponding ID. Roughly half of the entities have already been identified; eventually, the label of that ID will be used.

csvlens demo/step2/entities_enriched.csv

[running]

	label	qid	category	wikidata_Label	author	author_label	..
1	Carson McCullers	Q238591	persons	Carson McCullers			
2	Faulkner	Q38392	persons	William Faulkner			
3	Frankie Jasmine Addams	Q187421793	persons	Frankie Addams			
4	Cocteau	Q83158	persons	Jean Cocteau			
5	Annemarie Clarac-Schwarzenbach	Q123368	persons	Annemarie Schwarzenbach			
6	Mick		persons				
7	Manhattan	Q11299	places	Manhattan			
8	Georgia	Q1428	places	Georgia			
9	America	Q38	places	United States			
10	Francia	Q142	places	France			
11	Stock	Q3579517	publishers	Stock			
12	The Heart is a Lonely Hunter	Q1645466	works	The Heart Is a Lonely Hunter	Q238591	Carson McCullers	
13	Reflections in a Golden Eye	Q3658454	works	Reflections in a Golden Eye	Q238591	Carson McCullers	
14	Frankie Addams	Q187421793	works	Frankie Addams			
15	The Member of the Wedding		works				
16	il cuore è un cacciatore solitario	Q1645466	citations	The Heart Is a Lonely Hunter			
17	To Annemarie Clarac-Schwarzenbach	Q123368	citations	Annemarie Schwarzenbach			
18	Lo stile è l'andatura dello scritto		citations				

The next steps are imminent, particularly in deciding the workflow. Questions remain about task assignment: is it the responsibility of one person, or should it follow document ownership? Each person with a document number will create a TEI file (see top right in their interface), and the system can notify collaborators via email, helping to reduce manual work. The first two steps of this workflow could already be applied to specific topics, as discussed on the first day.

→ Question: LLM's performed differently after each prompt. Do you plan to validate or choose?

Peter Dängeli: they are not sure how much time they can invest, so they will just try one LLM and go with it. They add that it might be possible to automatically check the results, but currently there is too much pressure to test other options.

→ Question: I recommend using something I made or currently use, to promote a "Benchmark for LLMs".

Levyn Bürki: says that the cost per prompt might make it difficult to follow all recommendations, so it is unclear how much one can rely on the prompts.

Participant: suggest another option: benchmark prompts.

→ Question to the panel: How do you position your approaches with regard to the others? What can be useful for PARES, for example? What do you take from this session?

Claudia Tassone: says that she appreciates that the goal is to facilitate their work, as Johannes Graën told in his talk.

Johannes Graën: says that the results cannot be trusted blindly. He adds that, in developing a workflow, most of it can be used, but human review of the output is necessary. The important thing is to find the right balance and connect humans with machines.

VII. Conclusion

Vincent Pailluson summed up the two-day workshop by highlighting how it offered a detailed journey through the workflow of digital scholarly projects. He emphasized the balance between establishing the foundations for TEI and developing approaches for entity recognition. As *Reto Baumgartner* explained, even with trained models, much manual work remains necessary. Human effort is crucial; not only to process data but also to explain and make technical tools usable for others. While AI and LLMs can support the work, projects must remain under human control to ensure reliability and quality.

Ursula Bähler thanked all participants for their contributions and for sharing the diverse approaches. The workshop allowed for discussion of the concrete challenges faced by each project.

Muriel Jorge appreciated the variety of projects and approaches presented. The sessions were particularly useful for exploring individual projects in depth, understanding different perspectives, and seeing how various tools can interact depending on project goals.

Yann Stricker found it valuable to engage with the community around specific projects and subjects. He thanked all participants for their input.

Overall, the workshop highlighted the importance of combining technical tools, human expertise, and collaboration to advance digital scholarly work, while ensuring transparency and maintainability across projects.